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Research Article

**THE EFFICACY OF INTRAVENOUS POLYMYXIN
(COLISTIN) AGAINST MULTIDRUG RESISTANT
ORGANISMS IN CHILDREN WITH SEPSIS****Hareesh, Mohammad Iqbal**
Ziauddin Medical University**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Over the past few decades, multi-drug resistant (MDR) recurrence of polymyxin remission, particularly in serious patients, with gram negative infections, Polymyxin was less toxic than before.

Objective: To determine the efficacy of intravenous polymyxin (Colistin) against multidrug resistant organisms in children with sepsis

Material and Methods: This case series study was conducted at department of Pediatrics, Ziauddin University Hospital, Karachi from November 2017 To May 2018. Total 195 patients who were culture positive (urine, blood, tracheal aspirate, CSF fluid) for MDR organisms were included. Polymyxin at dose of 5 mg/kg/day, in 3 divided doses was started and continued for 21 days. Success of the medication was assessed according to microorganism growth in control cultures, together with clinical and radiographic improvements after 48 hrs of medication. Descriptive statistics were calculated. Stratification was done and post stratification chi-square test was applied. P-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results: There were 78.5% male and 21.5% female patients. Mean age was 6.19 ± 2.5 years. Mean weight after 48 hours of treatment was 2.36 ± 0.68 kg. Mean therapy duration was 6.62 ± 3.91 days. Mean therapy dose was 69647.69 ± 95789.41 IU. Mean hospital stay was 11.71 ± 5.84 days. Most common source of the micro-organism was blood. X-rays of 52.3% were found improved after 48 hours of treatment. Efficacy was among 90.3% patients.

Conclusion: With 90.3% efficacy, polymyxin was well tolerated and better option for the management of MDR-GNB infections.

Keywords: Efficacy, Intravenous Polymyxin (Colistin), Multidrug Resistant Organisms, Sepsis.

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INTRODUCTION:

Multidrug resistant (MDR) Gram-negative bacteria sepsis is a test globally these days.¹ Polymyxin-resistant Gram negative pathogens have also been found worldwide and has caused deaths and high medical costs.^{2,3} There are many cases of resistance, associated with excessive use and malpractice, in medical institutions.⁴ A study from Eastern part of India had described that around 27 percent of neonates died mainly because of MDR Gram-negative bacilli infections.⁵

In last 10years, just five novel antibiotics came into being and approved.⁶ Thus, there is a resurgence of previous antibiotics, like polymixin, as a final resort for treating MDR-gram-negative infections.⁷ Polymyxins, found out in 1940s, a group of polycationic peptide antibiotics, are showing good results in curing gram negative infections. Merely polymyxin B and E (colistin), which have structural variation of single amino acid among 5 chemical substances (A-E) of polymyxin, have been practically approved. During 1970s, these had virtually been ceased due to grave untoward effects in patients. Over the past 10years, MDR-resistant gram-negative infections have led to the use of polymixin, particularly in serious patients, because these have shown fewer side effects than previously reported.⁸ Polymyxins can be administered topically, I/M, IV and by inhalation.⁹ Some studies showed that once a day therapy will not be helpful against these organisms due to its short half life (4hrs).^{10,11}

According to a study by Jajoo et al, intravenous colistin was given to all the infants having MDR gram negative infections. After giving intravenous colistin most of the patients showed no microorganism growth and only 4 patients showed positive microorganism growth. 76 % infants with MDR gram negative infections responded to intravenous colistin^{12,13}. Another study showed that 91.7% of the infants with MDR gram negative infection successfully treated with intravenous colistin¹⁴. The use of intravenous colistin and its success in the form of good response to medication varies shown in different studies. The success of this medication in different pediatric age groups ranges from 72 % to 98% shown in different clinical studies¹⁵⁻²⁰. The dose of intravenous colistin which can be safely used in neonates and infants is still unclear. 2.5-5 mg/kg/day and 5.4±0.6 mg/kg/day doses reported in multicentre studies are safely used in neonates and other pediatric age groups^{21,22}. Jajoo et al¹² used the IV dose colistin as 50,000-75,000 IU/kg/day (1mg colistimethate sodium=12,500 IU) in neonatal care unit and 2.5-5 mg/kg/day dose was used by Alan et al¹⁶.

Jajoo et al reported that infants were given I/V

colistin for MDR gram-negative infections. After medication, microorganism growth was present in 4 patients and they found the medication was 76% successful.^{12,13} In another study we established that intravenous colistin was 91.7% successful.¹⁴ Different clinical studies have shown that the success of intravenous colistin on newborns and pediatric age group ranges between 72%-98%.¹⁵⁻²⁰ Further, currently, the safe dose of intravenous colistin in newborns and preterm infants is not known. However, according to the multicenter studies in recent years, 2.5-5 mg/kg/day and 5.4±0.6 mg/kg/day doses are safe in the pediatric age group.^{21,22} Jajoo et al.¹² reported using 50,000-75,000 IU/kg/day (1mg colistimethate sodium=12,500 IU) in newborns and preterm infants, while Alan et al.¹⁶ reported using 2.5-5 mg/kg/day.

In another study, intravenous colistin was used in 5 mg/kg/day dose for all patients. Most research has been conducted on adults and newborns. Since there is no information on children particularly in severe ones, so purpose of this research is to establish the polymixin's effectiveness among pediatrics infected with multidrug resistant organisms. In case of significant effectiveness of polymixin, we can devise a strategy of advising polymyxin in patients who will be found infected with multidrug resistant organisms in order to improve outcome by decreasing mortality, morbidity.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

This case series research was done at department of Pediatrics, Ziauddin University Hospital, Karachi, from November 2017 To May 2018. The non probability consecutive sampling was used for sampling. Total 195 children having any sex with age 3 to 12 years who were culture positive (urine, blood, tracheal aspirate, CSF fluid) for MDR organisms were included. Patients who either culture negative or positive for commonly used drugs i.e. aminoglycosides, quinolones, penicillins, all cephalosporins and inhibitor combinations, monobactams, or carbapenems were expelled from the research. Prior permission was also taken for induction in the study.

Multidrug resistant organisms were defined as the organisms that were resistant to at least 3 of the drugs i.e. Aminoglycosides, Quinolones, Penicillins, cephalosporins, and inhibitor combinations, monobactams, carbapenems. The success of medication was assessed according to microorganism growth in control cultures (blood, catheter, CSF, and tracheal aspirate) taken at least 3 day after intravenous colistin treatment, together with clinical (Weight, Blood Pressure, Urine output) and radiographic improvements.

Improvement was labeled positive when baseline findings were increased after 48 hrs of medication. In all included study subjects, polymyxin at dosage of 5 mg/kg/day tds was begun and continued for 21 days.

Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used for data compilation and analysis. Frequencies and percentages were computed for qualitative variables. Quantitative variables were presented as mean±standard deviation. Effect modifiers were controlled through stratification. Post stratification Chi-square test was applied and P-value ≤0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

Mean age was 6.19±2.5 years. Mean gestational age was 35.35±3.99 weeks. Mean weight at the time of admission was 2.29±0.75 kg. Mean onset infection time was 7.09±5.62 days. Mean therapy duration was 6.62±3.91 days. Mean therapy dose was 69647.69±95789.41 IU. Mean hemoglobin, total leukocyte count, platelets, C-reactive protein, urea, creatinine, sodium, potassium, chloride, H₂CO₃, prothrombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time, urine output and blood pressure at the time of admission was 13.38±2.58g/dL, 14.62±13.66x10⁹/L,

198.57±162.23x10⁹/L, 23.15±30.79mg/dL, 41.41±30.14mg/dL, 0.80±0.76μmol/L, 140.26±12.75mmol/L, 4.62±4.43 mmol/L, 105.31±11.73mmol/L, 22.07±5.80g/cm³, 17.05±4.06sec, 36.48±9.31sec, 2.06±1.18ml, and 59.98±11.26mmHg respectively. The detailed results are presented in Table-1.

After 48 hours of treatment the mean weight was 2.36±0.68 kg. The mean hemoglobin, total leukocyte count, platelets, C-reactive protein, urea, creatinine, sodium, potassium, chloride, H₂CO₃, prothrombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time, urine output and blood pressure was 13.16±2.63g/dL, 11.70±9.37x10⁹/L, 196.80±144.64x10⁹/L, 43.77±45.08mg/dL, 44.83±33.95mg/dL, 0.94±0.69μmol/L, 142.64±6.58mmol/L, 4.01±1.08mmol/L, 103.90±6.13mmol/L, 24.45±7.59g/cm³, 15.38±5.65sec, 34.19±11.11sec, 2.29±1.45ml, and 50.69±16.69mmHg respectively. The detailed results are presented in Table-2.

The age, weight at admission, onset infection time, and therapy dose were further stratified in groups. Frequency and Percentages are presented in Graph-1 tot Graph-4.

Table-1: Descriptive statistics of parameters at the time of admission

Total (n=195)	Mean±SD	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Range
Age (years)	6.19±2.25	6.00	3	12	9
Gestational Age (Weeks)	35.35±3.99	38.00	26	42	16
Weight (Kg)	2.29±0.75	2.30	0.80	4.50	3.70
Onset Infection Time (Days)	7.09±5.62	5.00	1	21	20
Therapy Duration (Days)	6.62±3.91	6.00	1	23	22
Therapy Dose (IU)	69647.69±95789.41	60000	3000	800000	797000
Hospital Stay (Days)	11.71±5.84	11.00	3	29	26
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	13.38±2.58	13.20	7.40	20.00	12.60
Total Leukocyte Count (10 ⁹ /L)	14.62±13.66	11.40	1.20	101	99.80
Platelets (10 ⁹ /L)	198.57±162.23	184.00	2.65	596.00	593.35
C-Reactive Protein (mg/dL)	23.15±30.79	13.04	0.18	155.03	154.85
Urea (mg/dL)	41.41±30.14	32.00	5	163	158
Creatinine (μmol/L)	0.80±0.76	0.70	0.10	6.69	6.59
Sodium (mmol/L)	140.26±12.75	143.00	48	152	104
Potassium (mmol/L)	4.62±4.43	4.00	2.30	39.00	36.70
Chloride (mmol/L)	103.51±11.73	104.00	1.30	116.00	114.70
H ₂ CO ₃ (g/cm ³)	22.07±5.80	22.00	6	35	29
Prothrombin Time (Sec)	17.05±4.06	16.39	10.40	29.10	18.70
Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (Sec)	36.48±9.31	34.30	19.60	69.80	50.20
Urine Output (ml)	2.06±1.18	1.75	0.26	6.09	5.83
Blood Pressure (mmHg)	59.98±11.26	64.00	26	77	51

Table-2: Descriptive statistics of parameters after 48 hours of treatment

Total (n=195)	Mean±SD	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Range
Weight (Kg)	2.36±0.68	2.40	0.80	4.50	3.70
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	13.16±2.63	12.90	5.00	18.90	13.90
Total Leukocyte Count (10 ⁹ /L)	11.70±9.37	7.60	1.60	45.50	43.90
Platelets (10 ⁹ /L)	196.80±144.64	175.00	6.00	969.00	690.00
C-Reactive Protein (mg/dL)	43.77±45.08	29.45	1.30	160.67	159.37
Urea (mg/dL)	44.83±33.95	36.00	15.00	253.00	238.00
Creatinine (μmol/L)	0.94±0.69	0.81	0.10	2.53	2.43
Sodium (mmol/L)	142.64±6.58	142.00	134.00	156.00	22.00
Potassium (mmol/L)	4.01±1.08	4.00	1.60	7.90	6.30
Chloride (mmol/L)	103.90±6.13	105.00	76.00	116.00	40.00
H ₂ CO ₃ (g/cm ³)	24.45±7.59	25.00	13.00	85.00	72.00
Prothrombin Time (Sec)	15.38±5.65	12.80	10.00	36.90	26.90
Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (Sec)	34.19±11.11	32.30	25.40	78.80	53.40
Urine Output (ml)	2.29±1.45	2.00	0.14	6.50	6.36
Blood Pressure (mmHg)	50.69±16.69	48.00	26.00	92.00	66.00

Graph-1: Percentage of patients according to stratified groups of age (n=195)

Out of 195 children, 78.5% were male and 21.5% were female. Most common source of the micro-organism was blood. It was also seen that 19.5% were found with infiltrates through chest x-ray at the time of admission while 52.3% were found better after 48 hours of medication. The success was found for 90.3% children. The detailed results are presented in Table-3.

The results showed significant connection of efficacy with weight at admission ($p=0.002$) and polymyxin therapy dose ($p=0.000$) while no significant connection was found with gender ($p=0.219$), age ($p=0.220$), onset

infection duration ($p=0.847$), and multidrug resistant organism source ($p=0.600$). The comprehensive outcomes of associations are explained from Table-4.

Table-3: Frequency distribution of gender, source, and x-ray findings

Total (n=195)		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	153	78.5
	Female	42	21.5
Source of Micro Organism (MDR)	Urine	6	3.1
	Blood	138	70.8
	Tracheal aspirate	42	21.5
	CS fluid	9	4.6
Chest X-Ray Findings At The Time of Admission	Air entry	8	4.1
	Air entry white shadowing	3	1.5
	Clear	6	3.1
	Complete white out	3	1.5
	Complete white some	3	1.5
	Good air entry	6	3.1
	Ground glass complete white	2	1.0
	Ground glass	5	2.6
	Infiltrates	6	3.1
	Left sided consolidation	2	1.0
	infiltrates	38	19.5
	Infiltrates +haziness	3	1.5
	Normal	31	15.9
	Patchy infiltrates	8	4.1
	Pneumo	3	1.5
	Pulmonary Infiltrates	3	1.5
	Slight Haziness	2	1.0
	White	12	6.2
	White complete	15	7.7
	White shadow air entry	28	14.4
	White shadowing on right side	6	3.1
	White+ Infiltrates	2	1.0
	Chest X-ray Findings After 48 Hours Of Treatment	Air entry improved	57
Air entry increased		3	1.5
Clear		8	4.1
Good air entry		4	2.1
Improved		102	52.3
Infiltrates		2	1.0
Normal		2	1.0
Not repected		2	1.0
Some		13	6.7
White		2	1.0
Efficacy		Yes	176
	No	19	9.7

Table-4: Association of efficacy with gender, age, duration of injury, and mode of injury

Total (n=195)		Efficacy			P-value
		Yes (n=176) n (%)	No (n=19) n (%)	Total	
Gender	Male	136 (88.9)	17 (11.1)	153	0.219**
	Female	40 (95.2)	2 (4.8)	42	
Age	≤5 years	76 (87.4)	11 (12.6)	87	0.220**
	>5 years	100 (92.6)	8 (7.4)	108	
Weight	≤2.5 kg	116 (85.9)	19 (14.1)	135	0.002*
	>2.5 kg	60 (100)	0 (0)	60	
Onset Infection Duration	≤ 7days	126 (90)	14 (10)	140	0.847**
	>7 days	50(90.9)	5 (9.1)	55	
Polymyxin Therapy Dose	≤60,000 IU	128 (96.2)	5 (3.8)	133	0.000*
	>60,000 IU	48 (77.4)	14 (22.6)	62	
Source Of Multidrug Resistant Organism	Urine	6 (100)	0 (0)	6	0.600**
	Blood	124 (89.9)	14 (10.1)	138	
	Tracheal aspirate	37 (89.1)	5 (11.9)	42	
	CS fluid	9 (100)	0 (0)	9	

* Significant at 0.05 levels using Chi Square test
** Not significant at 0.05 levels using Chi Square test

DISCUSSION:

MDR-gram-ve rods, commonly found in studies with frequency in descending order are *Acinetobacter* species, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *E.coli* and *Pseudomonas*.²⁴ But during one more research researchers found *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas* the main multidrug resistant organisms.²⁵ Drug resistant *Acinetobacter species*, hence grueling to act towards are increasing in number.^{24,26-27} Carbapenem resistance in *Klebsiella* and *Pseudomonas* is furthermore increasing. So, malpractice and mishandling of broad spectrum antibiotics has played a role in contributing this resistance.²⁸ The current study reported a high number of MDR gram negative infections. During one more research, the collective incidence of gram negative blood stream infection was 5.4/1000 hospital admissions. Among them 39% were MDR gram negative infections.²⁵

Siddiqui NR reported a death number of 42.9% in patients infected with MDR gram negative organisms. Among them 75% were infants in comparison to general death rate of 12.3%.²⁶

According to previous research, death rate was between 10–53.6%.^{25,29-32} But it is fractious to fortify the reason behind demise, was the resistance, critical condition, overuse of antibiotics or co morbidities! The frequent causes of infection among significantly sick patients are allied to exposure to invasive procedures, underlying disease, long time admission in ICU, antibiotic use and consagiousness.³³ Two polymyxins are used clinically, Polymyxin B and Polymyxin E; but knowledge regarding their pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics is still not sufficient.³⁴ There are limited reports on use of polymyxin B in pediatric age group.^{29,30} There were only few studies investigating the use of polymyxin B for the

treatment of infections caused by MDR-gram negative pathogens, mostly *Acinetobacter* and *Pseudomonas*.³⁵⁻³⁷ Siddiqui NR reported data of fourteen significantly sick pediatric patients, who received intravenous polymyxin B but despite this almost 50% of them expired.² Formerly reported death toll amid MDR-gram negative infected patients with Polymyxin use was 20-54%³⁵⁻³⁸ which is equivalent to our data. By the way, it is complex to determine what the cause was whether Polymyxin B or other risk factors like severity of the underlying illness and co morbidities etc. Side effects of parental Polymyxin B which were reported were related to kidney and nervous system. Incidence of nephrotoxicity ranges from 0-37%.³⁹ Siddiqui NR in addition detected an analogous rate of toxicity to kidney. It is arduous to confirm what the cause was, whether the underlying kidney disease or concomitantly used other nephrotoxic drug with Polymyxin or primarily a plane stimulate of Polymyxin B itself.²⁶ Mild damage to nervous system that is produced due to Polymyxin B reverses after stoppage of treatment.³⁹ Signs of Polymyxin B

induced neurotoxicity include dizziness, generalized muscle weakness, facial or peripheral paresthesia, partial deafness, visual disturbances, vertigo, confusion, hallucinations, seizures, ataxia, and neuromuscular weakness.³⁶

Limiting determination of risk factors for mortality among MDR gram negative patients and inability to comment on the nephrotoxicity of polymyxin the present study is a nonrandomized, observational study, and is thus limited by patient selection bias. This study was a single hospital-based study with a small sample size therefore, the results might not be generalizable to larger populations.

CONCLUSION:

In our study, with the 90.3% efficacy, it was concluded that polymyxin was well tolerated by children and it appears to be a good choice for the treatment of MDR-GNB infections. Combination therapy may achieve high cure rates and is advised for MDR-GNB infections.

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